

**A
Literature Review
On
Fault Tolerance-Based Mechanisms
in
Distributed Systems**

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Abstract

This study covers the three fault-tolerant strategies that are used in distributed systems, followed by the analysis of two authors[12], who verified and confirmed that employing fusion $O(n)$ spaces saves when compared to replication, and theoretically demonstrated that they have a low overhead while operating normally. Similarly, an examination of the paper [13] reveals that while fusion-based space savings do exist, they come at a very high recovery time cost. Therefore, one should carefully weigh that expense.

Introduction

Many independent components that are spread across various machines and share messages in distributed systems work together to accomplish shared objectives. Fault tolerance is thus included in distributed systems in order to combat a single point of failure and achieve high availability and business continuity of systems. As a result, various strategies built on fault tolerance have been introduced[2]. Replication-based, redundancy-based, fusion-based, and other common strategies are a few. A fault-tolerant system's main objective is to continue operating even if one component develops a defect. As a result, it prioritizes availability and reliability while addressing users' concerns[2]

Replication-Based Mechanisms

Fig 1. Replication-based technique in a distributed system[2]

Synchronization of states between redundant nodes is a function of replication-based techniques. Here, redundant resources communicate information to maintain consistency. Some criteria, such as linearizability, sequential consistency, causal consistency, etc., maintain the consistency of the data. Contrary to causal consistency, which establishes a weak consistency criterion, sequential and linearizability consistency assure strong consistency. The primary backup replication, voting, and primary-per-partition replication are some of the protocols used by the replication approaches for replicating data or an object. For instance, the linearizability of a primary backup

replication strategy and an active replication technique both ensure consistency. A request can be issued to one replica system while the other replica system is still receiving it using the replication mechanisms. In the degree of replication, to attain a high level of consistency, a large number of replicas is needed. Major issues in replication-based techniques are consistency, degree of replica, replica on demand, etc. In a distributed database, the process of duplicating and maintaining database objects in multiple places is referred to as replication. In a distributed system, there are three different types of replication: snapshot, transactional, and merge.

Fig. 2. Active vs Passive Replication [2]

All of the servers process the client's request in active replication. To send the requests to all of the servers in the same order, a broadcast protocol is required. When using passive replication, the primary server responds to client requests while the backup servers take over. Response times are longer in this replication because there is only one server handling numerous client requests.

Redundancy-Based Mechanisms

Fig. 3. Process Redundancy[2]

Implementations of distributed mechanisms can be made more robust by using redundancy[2]. It can be used to create distributed systems that are compatible with computing and communication. Single-node deviations can be identified by sending signals down numerous channels in a biconnected network, where there are at least two independent paths connecting any two nodes.[2] Informally, this indicates that several disjoint pathways connect the nodes and are used to transmit copies of messages (such as node inputs or computation-related information). Some group of alternative nodes may be designated to receive and carry out computations in the decentralized mechanism case, when computing is dispersed over the network. Both active and passive redundancy are possible.[2] In the passive instance, traffic is received by one node here, and in the event of a failure, switching to another node is performed to achieve reliability. In this manner, a single point of failure will be prevented.[2]

Fusion-Based Mechanisms:

Fig.4. Fusion-Based Method[2]

[2] The data structures (queue, stack, etc.) on servers in distributed systems are vulnerable to crash faults, which can result in a complete loss of state. The most common method of tolerating crash faults is replication. Replication involves making a complete copy of the original data and storing it. As a result, space efficiency is gained, and a smaller number of backups than replication can be used to tolerate crash defects. Replication is hence the fault tolerance strategy or approach that is most frequently used. Replication necessitates f replicas of each data structure, resulting in nf extra backups, to tolerate f crash faults among n different data structures. For backups that can withstand f crash defects with merely f additional fused backups, fused data structures are utilized. When using fusion, space efficiency is achieved by tolerating f crash faults with f fused backups. [2] It takes up more space to keep nf additional backups for n different data structures. As a result, it is far more precise, dependable, and adaptive. The fusion-based solution fixes that issue because administration costs are highly expensive, and backups grow as problems grow. Fusion-based technique is an alternative to the replication-based technique because it requires fewer backup devices. [2] The backup machines are fused in accordance with the specified set of machines, as depicted in Figure 4. The recovery method for the fusion-based technique has a relatively large overhead, although it is tolerable for systems with minimal probabilities of fault. This way, fusion-based design can result in significant savings in space as well as resources.[2]

Many times, distributed systems are modeled as a collection of separate servers communicating with clients via messages. Servers frequently maintain numerous instances of data structures in order to store and manipulate data efficiently[7]. These servers' issues can fall into one of two categories: crash faults [8] or Byzantine faults [12]. In the case of Byzantine faults, servers can have any state of the data structures, but in the event of crash faults, the server crashes and the

data structures are lost. In the work [10], fusion is created by combining the best of both worlds to accomplish the minimal update overhead of replication and the space efficiency of coding. It uses little storage, and replication recovery is inexpensive.[12]

It uses little storage, and replication recovery is inexpensive. In the system design of this paper[12], several separate distributed servers hosted various data structures. Assume there are n primary data structures, each with its own host. Fused backups in this context are those data structures created with the intention of fusing primary data. These data structures experience Byzantine or crash defects. No updates are transmitted by the clients following a problem until all failed data structures have been restored to their original states. The authors of [1] provide data structures for list-based primary and any array. The authors of [12] provide a generalized fused backup for the most popular data structures, such as lists, tacks, and vectors.

Fig.5. Old fusion [1]

The developers of [1] provided a design to fuse primary linked lists to fix a single crash problem. A linked list with each node containing the xor of the primary values makes up the fused structure. Each node has a bit array of size n , where each bit denotes whether a primary element is present in that node.

Fig. 6. Fused Backups for LinkedLists[12]

It displays two primary linked lists and two fused backups that can fix two primary linked list flaws. The elements a_1 and b_1 are contained in the fused node in the 0th place at the backups, with F_1 storing their sum and F_2 carrying their difference. We additionally save auxiliary structures that replicate the index data of the primary at each fused backup in addition to the stack.

<pre> INSERT at Primaries $X_i :: i = 1..n$ Input: key k, data value d; if ($primLinkedList \cdot contains(k)$) /* key present, just update its value*/ $old = primLinkedList \cdot get(k) \cdot value$ $primLinkedList \cdot update(k, p)$; $send(k, d, old)$ to all fused backups; else /* key not present, create new node*/ $primNode = new primNode$; $p \cdot value = d$; $auxNode a = new auxNode$; $a \cdot primNode = p$; $p \cdot auxNode = a$; /* mimic backup stack */ $auxList.insertAtEnd(a)$; $primLinkedList \cdot insert(k, p)$; $send(k, d, null)$ to all fused backups; </pre>	<pre> INSERT at Fused Backups $F_j :: j = 1..t$ Input: key k, new value d_i, old value old_i; if ($auxLinkedList[i] \cdot contains(k)$) $fusedNode f = auxLinkedList[i] \cdot get(k)$; $f \cdot updateCode(old_i, d_i)$; else $fusedNode p = tos[i] ++$; if ($p == null$) $p = new fusedNode$; $dataStack \cdot insert(p)$; $dataStackTos ++$; $p \cdot updateCode(0, d_i)$; $p \cdot refCount ++$; /* mimic primary linked list */ $auxNode a = new auxNode$; $a \cdot fusedNode = p$; $p \cdot auxNode[i] = a$; $auxLinkedList[i] \cdot insert(k, a)$; </pre>
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Fig. Fused Backups for Linked Lists: Inserts(12)

The algorithms for inserting a key-value pair at the primary and backup databases are depicted in the previous figure. In every primary. We also keep an auxiliary list that functions similarly to the backup stack in addition to the main data structure.

<p>DELETE at Primaries $X_i :: i = 1..n$</p> <p>Input: key k; $p = primLinkedList \cdot delete(k)$; $old = p \cdot value$; /* tail node of aux list points to top-most element of X_i at backup stack */ $auxNode \ auxTail = auxList \cdot getTail()$; $tos = auxTail \cdot primNode \cdot value$; $send(k, old, tos)$ to all fused backups; $auxNode \ a = p \cdot auxNode$; /* shift tail of aux list to replace a */ $(a \cdot prev) \cdot next = auxTail$; $auxTail \cdot next = a \cdot next$; $delete \ a$;</p>	<p>DELETE at Fused Backups $F_j :: j = 1..t$</p> <p>Input: key k, old value old_i, end value tos_i; /* update fused node containing old_i with primary element of X_i at $tos[i]$*/ $auxNode \ a = auxLinkedList[i] \cdot delete(k)$; $fusedNode \ p = a \cdot fusedNode$; $p \cdot updateCode(old_i, tos_i)$; $tos[i] \cdot updateCode(tos_i, 0)$; $tos[i] \cdot refCount --$; /* update aux node pointing to $tos[i]$ */ $tos[i] \cdot auxNode[i] \cdot fusedNode = p$; if ($tos[i].refCount == 0$) $dataStackTos --$; $tos[i] --$;</p>
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Fig.7. Fused Backups for Linked lists: Delete[12]

The above figure shows the algorithms for the deletion of a key at the primaries and the backups. Given n basic data structures, a fusion-based method ensures space savings in this way [12]. Two authors compared active replication and fusion with a distributed system in [13]. They were able to present two apps that had been specifically created for each mechanism in this way. [13] In their studies, they deployed the application in a variety of configurations and assessed the performance of each one in terms of three characteristics: the amount of time needed to update, the amount of space used for backups, and the amount of time needed for a wrecked node to recover. Regarding updating time, the results were inconsistent as shown in fig 8.

# of groups g	# of nodes n	
	Fusion	Active replication
1	1	2
2	2	4
3	3	6
4	4	8
5	5	10

Fig.8. Node configurations for experimental runs ($f=1$)[13]

Fig. 9. Backup space results[13] Fig. 10 Recovery time results (Active result vs fusion) [13]

In fig. 9, their experiment demonstrates that the fusion backup's space requirements are linearly related to the size of the data structure being backed up. But while replication is active, backups. The copies of their data grow together with the number of nodes n and groups g , and the backup space must correspondingly grow as well. It's interesting to see that the active replication schema takes up less room for small n . As opposed to the active replication application, where the replicated nodes merely keep a list of bits.

In Figure 10, it is evident that replication outperforms fusion under any node arrangement. Therefore, it can be inferred from this experiment that, although space savings are significant for a system having a sufficient number of backed-up nodes, the savings come at the expense of a very long recovery time. Systems with few crash defects and minimal to no high-availability needs may benefit the most from the practical application of fusions. In addition, more broadly applicable frameworks are utilized to support the development community to aid in the growth of fusion adoption.

Conclusion:

In this paper, I explained the three fault tolerance techniques and how they are used in distributed systems. After reading the studies listed in the references, I also gained insight into how active replication might be contrasted with the fusion-based fault tolerance solution. A fusion-based technique, given the n primary data structures, ensures space savings, but [13] argued that these savings came at the expense of a very long recovery time. Therefore, one should carefully weigh that expense. This demonstrates that fusion results in enormous space, power, and resource savings.

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